
Human Beings with 90% Mental Disability States and their Impacts on Individuals with Good Mental Health States Exposes to the Same Mental Health Facility and Similar Conditions of Treatment.

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ABSTRACT

Man's ability to have total control of oneself and coordinates all activities in daily life depends on absolute good or healthy state of the mind. The mind is the master control room of every being on earth. And with this mind in its good state or correct state of mind, one can behave very well. Once there is a change in the state of the mind as a result of inhibitor of the mind, once attitudes of behaviour changes. Such changes in behaviour, attitudes or motives can be attributed to drug abuse, breakages in marriages, failure in examinations or life, loss of loved one, loss of job, accidents, spiritual attack etc. Such individuals most at times experiences mental shocks hence mental illness or sufferings. Such people are always sent to mental homes or mental health facilities for rehabilitation or seek for help to bring the individual's mind to a state of public acceptability for self-control and coordination in daily life. With such facilities and structures in place to address issues of such nature, bad motivated and get rich people (Ocultic world powers) makes use of spiritual powers to generate people who then get exposed to such incapacitated people in mental health facilities in Ghana. Such people of good mental health status exposed to all kinds of treatments and dangers when sent to such facilities with mindset of having the same problem. Such people end up being dragged into the problem and ending up as mentally disable (98% in mental disability) people of no return into natural mental status of public usage and missing among good mental health people again. They go into a state of total mental illness and darkness and seen as mad people of no concern and usage to the public and country again.

Keywords: mental, health, disability, brain, mind, spiritual, psychoactive, Ocultic, behaviour, rehabilitation, drug abuse, treatment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Life activities on the planet earth mainly depends on the mind and the sense organs. Coordination between them is what gives

the mankind a sense of direction when looking at daily activities. A mind can be full of activities to be accomplished in a day, but a break in chain can be attributed to a change in mind

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or faulty in thought which is centered on the mind. The mind has its associated problems just like the way the body fights its illnesses on daily basis in order to stay healthy. The mind can never attain 100% efficiency when it comes to its actions, capability and ability. Notwithstanding, any break in the minds coordination in serving as the master control room is a big problem and danger to the individuals or beings involved. Life is never complete without the mind, hence doctors ensure brain functionality during and after every delivery of a baby for a perfect life on earth. Any malfunctioning of the brain results in all kinds of uncoordinated behaviour and actions. Hence any individual with a normal daily life full of acceptable activities is seen as a normal person. Once there is an observed change in Behaviour, motive, attitude and actions is said to be a mentally ill or sick and the need for medical attention. This is the case in daily life in Ghana. Such mental issues or problems do not just happen or occur in our lives. Most mental problems are as a result of activities such as broken homes, failed marriages, failed examinations, delivery issues, drug abuse, smoking of weed and shisha, loss of loved ones, deportation from abroad, disasters (such as flooding and air masses), excessive sex, spiritual attacks from Occultic world and higher realms etc. The resultant impacts of these listed scenarios is loss of mind and uncoordinated activities which makes life difficult.

The cerebrum, cerebellum, and medulla oblongata coordinates all activities of the mind for total control achievement of purpose, goals and objectives on daily basis. Any damage to any of the parts or chain has is associated repercussions. All kinds

of people are exposed to mental health facilities in Ghana and worldwide especially those with the problems listed above. Such people have their mental states disabled to an extent. It can be to 50%, 55%, 60%, 67%, 70%, 78%, 80% etc and the need for work to be done on them for such minds to be brought to normality and originality for perfect coordination in life. With such instability in mind, individuals in such positions exhibit all kinds of actions and behaviors. Some of these actions, attitudes and behaviors includes talking to oneself, staying alone for longer hours, walking aimlessly, picking of things on refuse dumps, wearing dirty clothes for months, walking in the middle of roads etc. Such minds have been lost to a higher degree for those on the streets and working on them is very difficult since the mind is about 93% out of order. But the once below 60% have a higher percentage of working on and bringing it to order or under control or even 95% once can be worked on and brought under control. But with such once, probability is 0.02 possibility. Bringing the mind under control is a very difficult task, since there is a distortion in creation and repairing creation is divinely influenced and nature has to give acceptance into code creation into nature. Since there is distortion in creation and orderliness, bringing the mind to order is not easy.

Spirituality also plays a role when assessing the number people subjected or exposed to mental health facilities in Ghana. Ghana as a country is recognized as Christian country per counting the number of churches in Ghana comparable to other worshippers. It is also seen as an Islamic country as well as

traditionalist. Hence Ghana seen as a country which does not play or joke with spiritual things or spirituality. With this in mind, everyone seen or believed to be rich in life should have an associated spiritual background whichever way. This is what some does by looking for others who will carry their cross in life hence the use of all kinds of super natural powers and means to make others victims while enriching themselves. Most victims of such adventure ends up on the streets or in mental homes looking for salvation keys to come back to normalcy. In some cases also, others do the enrichment journey themselves but ends up losing the mind and finds themselves on the streets of Ghana and Africa. Such people are unable to break secret codes of treasure hunting covered with madness and ends there. Such people also ends up in mental homes looking for help to return back to healthy mental states.

Assuming an intellectual is manipulated and ends in a mental home or facility with the same states of conditions and treatments for good health, you can think of the consequences. This is the case most graduates finds themselves in Ghana after a four year duration degree program, master's degree program of PHD's. Such people gets their educated heads exposed to such predicaments and can be generated into a higher degree problem in life. This is a reality problem as individuals who have toiled and educated themselves to to that level of even PHD's gets their heads formatted and installed into heads of uneducated people of another world for such people to make a learning and education career in life. I think they are of the

view that, one PHD head and its exit from life or earth can give twenty folds of educated people of lower class in Ghana.

This is the case of situations for some people in Ghana which belong to a world and being worked against another world. When such instances occurs once can see the world subjecting the world to all kinds of problems listed above to end and individual in a mental health facility with all forces of nature and different dimensions of accusations. If such an individual doesn't get an individual or good nature to work on his behalf or force so force of nature to backs his effort of fighting against such a cause and world, that soul is gone for good. Mental health facilities therefore exist to protect and fight for such victims but continues use of drugs to curtain the problem works on the brain negatively and the person ends up as a drug addict or victim of circumstances. Exposure and out of the mental health facility has its consequences. Stigmatization by people after being treated on drugs and subsequent going to the facility makes life difficult to live with if not of strong mind. Even the educated in Ghana have a problem with such people or people with mental health problems. They think once subjected to mental health facilities, then the head and mind is out of order and not programmable to work again or coordinated to function effectively. Mental health problems and issues can be associated with anyone hence the need for no stigmatization by any one. Assuming being arrested by five strong men, forced and sent to the mental health facility and treated harshly after which a sleeping injection is given for you to sleep for hours. After waking up, you find yourself locked up and no way out

of the facility and it happens three times to you. It can create a problem for you. In doing this, once brain is formatted and your intelligence into a system and become a routine thing done anytime one wants to builds his/her intelligence to a higher degree or level and everybody sees it. Won't it be a routine for everyone who wants to access the head, intelligence or information gotten? This is a real time scenario generated on several occasions and people of no intelligence are using in Ghana to access intelligence and brains to make a living. This can create a problem for one at home, at the work place, among peers, in the community, in the church and among social groups etc. If not handled carefully, such a person will lose his/her mind, goes mad, become a nuisance and finally ends in death. If death does not occur, stigmatization can even lead to madness or lonely life. Some even ends up becoming a burden on families and friends with them acting as if they love the 100% and the feel their situations. This brain formatting and installation is what is generating kids of high accepted IQ's but after getting degrees and PHD's, one do not see their impact on country and generations. It therefore deems fit for occupation therapist (OT), psychiatric doctors, and health professionals such as counsellors to be very careful when dealing with mental health problems.

In a way, most people end up as mental health patients on their way to treasure hunting in life. Wealth is spiritually bound and most wealth and treasures are spiritually covered. Hence the need to embark on spiritual journey before assessing the treasure. This is the case among gold treasure hunters in Ghana

especially illegal gold miners. In Ghana, illegal gold miners believes gold mining has its associated spirits which needs to be worked on before assessing the treasure. Anyone who fails to do this rites may end up as mad or even in death. This is the reality for most of the people one finds in mental health facilities in Ghana and was seen during this work with real time investigations. Divine creation rendered unto mankind the Garden of Eden where man was authorized to have dominion and nurture the garden towards beauty and self-freedom. This was mainly dependent on man's ability to make use of his mind, think like the creator and nurture it. Man faulted after being deceived by the enemy and resulted in a limitation placed on man. The beautiful treasure given to mankind was lost and the creation was taken over by the enemy with the enemy becoming the new owner. This new owner has total control over earth's creation and now plays the tune for whoever wants to be rich to dance by it and become rich. Hence to be rich or access greater wealth in life, one ought to access the wealth or riches through evil means of which most ends up in psychiatric wards as mental patients looking for treatments. It is therefore necessary to understand the mental make-up of mankind, the psychological behaviour of people and how they think when it comes to their daily way of life and happenings. The human brain which is the master control room of the body ought to be analyzed for its make-up and functionality so that any shortfall can be worked on.

2 Related Works on Mental Health and associated problems

2.1 The Human Brain

The human brain is the control room of the body spearheading all affairs of mankind. Some brain structures are clearly demarcated. Others gradually merge into others; this leads to debate about their exact boundaries and the functions they control (Atkinson et. al., 1990). All the neurons in the brain and the spinal cord makes up the central nervous system. The human brain is composed of three centric layers; a) central core b) the limbic system c) the cerebral hemisphere (together known as the cerebral hemisphere (Atkinson et. al., 1990). The central core includes most of the brain stem. The first slight enlargement of the spinal cord as it enters the skull is the medulla, a narrow structure that control breathing and some reflexes that help the organism maintains upright posture (Atkinson et. al., 1990). Attached to the rear of the brain stem is a convoluted structure called the cerebellum. The cerebellum is primarily concerned with coordination of movement. Located just above the brain stem inside the cerebral hemispheres are two egg – shaped groups of nerves cell nuclei that make up the thalamus. One region of the thalamus acts as a relay station and directs incoming information to the cerebellum from the sense receptors for vision, touch, hearing and taste. Another region of the thalamus plays an important in the control of sleep and wakefulness (Atkinson et. al., 1990). Any injury to this region of the thalamus that plays a role in sleeping and wakefulness may have effects on once sleep and hence the resultant mental problem.

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2.2 Neurons, nerves and Coordination

Even though neurons differ, they have certain common characteristics. Projecting from the cell body are a number of short branches called dendrites (Atkinson et. al., 1990). The dendrites and cell body receive neural impulses from adjacent neurons. These massages are transmitted to other neurons by a slender extension of the cell called an axon. At the end of the axon branch into a number of fine collaterals that end in small swellings called synaptic terminals. When neural impulses travels down the axon and arrives at the synaptic terminals, it triggers the secretion of a chemical called neurotransmitter. Although all neurons have these general features, they vary greatly in size and shape (Atkinson et. al., 1990). There are three types of neurons; sensory neurons transmit impulses received by receptors to the central nervous system. The receptors are specialized cells in the sense organs, muscles, skin and joints that detect physical or chemical changes and translate these into impulses that travels along the sensory neurons. (Atkinson et. al., 1990). This is what makes someone to be able to feel hotness or coldness or even fire whenever there is any physical changes in the environment. Motor neurons carry ongoing signals from the brain or spinal cord to the effector organs namely the muscles and glands. Coordination of these neurons with other sense organs is what gives someone a good mental state of mind towards fulfillment of daily activities

2.3 Asymmetries in the Brain

On examination of the brain in much details, the two halves of the human brain look like mirror images of each other. But closer examination reveals asymmetries. When brains are measured during autopsies, the left hemisphere is almost always larger than the right hemisphere (Atkinson et. al., 1990). Also, the right hemisphere contains many long neural fibres that connect widely separate areas of the brain, whereas the left hemisphere contains many shorter fibres that provide rich interconnection within a limited area (Geschwind et. al., 1987). Paul Broca (1861) examined the brains of a patient who had suffered speech loss and found that there are damages in areas of the left hemisphere just above the lateral fissure in the frontal lobe. The region known as Broca's area is involved in the production of speech (Broca, 1861). Hence a damage or loss to a higher degree of such a region will subject an individual to a mental health facility for diagnosis and treatment. In this case the mentally ill individual is expected to show all kinds of mentally sick attitudes and behaviour.

2.4 Drug dependence

Since ancient times, people have used drugs to alter their state of mind, consciousness – to stimulate or relax, to bring sleep, prevent sleep, to enhance ordinary perception or to produce hallucinations (Atkinson et. al., 1990). Psychoactives are drugs that affect behaviour, consciousness or mood. They include not only street drugs such as heroin and marijuana but also stimulants such as alcohol, tobacco and coffee. Table 1 list and

classifies the psychoactive drugs that are commonly used and abused.

Table 1: Psychoactives drugs that are commonly used

<i>Psychoactives</i>	Commonly Used
1. <i>Depressants (Sedatives)</i>	Alcohol (ethanol), Barbiturates, minor tranquilizers, valium.
2. <i>Opiates (Narcotics)</i>	Opium and its derivatives, Heroin, Morphine, Methadone.
3. <i>Stimulants</i>	Cocaine, Nicotine, Caffeine, Amphetamines, Bensedrine
4. <i>Hallucinogenes</i>	Mescaline, Psilocybin,
5. <i>Cannabis</i>	Marijuana, Hashish

Source: Atkinson et. al., 1990.

It may be difficult to appreciate the major changes in patterns of drug usage and taken behaviour over the past 100years. For instance, the widespread use of tranquilizers for the treatment of mental illness and emotional problems which began in the 1950's and the appearance of oral contraception's in 1960 did much to change people attitudes towards drugs (Atkinson et. al., 1990). All of the drugs listed in **Table 1** are assumed to affect behaviour and consciousness because they act in specific biochemical ways on the brain. With repeated usage, an individual can become physically or psychologically dependent on any of these drugs (Atkinson et. al., 1990). The United States still has the highest rates of drug usage among the world's industrialized nations (Johnson et. al., 1989).

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2.5 Effects of Alcohol

Drugs that depress the central nervous system includes the minor tranquilizers, barbiturates and alcohols. In small quantities, alcohol appears to increase people's energy and make them feel lively and sociable. In reality, it is a central nervous system depressant, not a stimulant. The initial stimulating effect of alcohol is believed to occur because the inhibiting synapses in the brain are depressed slightly earlier than the excitation synapses. Since the brain's neurons maintain a close balance between excitation and inhibition, the depression of inhibitory synapses results in a feeling of excitation, or stimulation. However, the excitation synapses soon become depressed too; the stimulating effects are overridden causing drowsiness and slowed sensory and motor functions. Continuous intake of such ethanol leads to mental retardation and disability (Atkinson et. al., 1990).

2.6 Sexual disorder and Behaviour

A great survey of British sexual attitudes and lifestyle (Johnson et. al., 1994) has provided the most comprehensive evaluation of sexual behaviour in the British public to date (Basant et. al., 1998). It was motivated largely by the emergence in 1980's of the lethal epidemic of sexually transmitted infection, HIV and lack of baseline measures of sexual behaviour. In the past four decades, the median age of first heterosexual intercourse has fallen from 21years to 17 years for women and 20years to 17years for men. People in the 21st century are more likely to use contraceptives (usually condoms and injections for women)

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than those of previous generations (Basant et. al., 1998). Frequency of heterosexual sex (oral, vaginal, anal intercourse) among the youth shows wide variability with a small proportion of the population reporting a very high frequency of sexual contact. Vaginal intercourse usually dominates when dealing with intercourse since that is the natural way and is the most preferred. Increase in practice of oral sex, but not as a substitute to vaginal intercourse.

In Ghana, the youth outside marriage have less frequent sex past overall but not today. For the current Ghana, they are more likely to have multiple partners, a wide range of practices and recent experiences of high risk practices (Basant et. al., 1998).

3 Research Area and Methodology

3.1 Research Area

The study area for this work is the Regional Hospital Koforidua (RHK) in the Eastern Region of Ghana, Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital – Kumasi in the Ashanti Region of Ghana and Pantang Hospital - Accra in the Greater Accra Region of Ghana. Koforidua is the capital city of the Eastern Region of Ghana. The city harbors people of total population of 127,334 (Ghana Statistical Service, 2012). Koforidua is the commercial heart for the eastern region and the New Juaben Municipal district. Koforidua lies on latitude 6° 05' 38" N and longitude 0° 15' 32" W at an elevation of 238m (781ft) above sea level. The New

Juaben municipality falls within the Eastern Region of south Ghana covering a total land area of 110km². This total land area constitutes 0.57% of the total land area of the Eastern Region. The annual rainfall over the capital ranges from 50inches to 120inches and 20°C to 32°C, mean annual temperature. The New Juaben municipality shares borders with East – Akim municipality to the northeast, Suhum Kraboa Coal tar district to the west, and Akwapim North district to the east and south. A number of industrial activities are embarked in the city and these include textiles, crafts, soap, traditional medicine, welders, carpentry, ceramics and pottery. Production of alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages and good bread forms part of industrialized produced products in the city. Regional Hospital Koforidua (RHK) is the main hospital within the region attending all issue of health which is above the horizon of the district hospitals in the region. The mental health department (MHD) is the department responsible for all mental health associated problems that the hospital receives on daily basis.

The study area also focus on Pantan Hospital in Accra where the same scenarios were being generated over and over again. The same happened in Kumasi which was the first place of case for scenario generation over and over again in Ghana as stated in the introduction. The main focus point is at Koforidua in the Eastern Region of Ghana

3.2 Methodology Employed

Research works always aims at establishing an inner truth about something. The main aim of this research work is to

access and analyze human beings with 90% mental disability state and see whether they can have significant impacts on same humans of good health status when all are exposed to same facility and treatment. This research work started when a health human being was arrested and sent to a mental health facility and subjected to harsh treatment equivalent to that for people of mental deficiencies. The method employed is the facility Stationed Focus Assessment and Evaluation Method (FSFAEM). In the process, investigator is tasked and goes through the normal process for patient of mental illness in the mental home. Results are generated after detail activities and picking of data and intelligence for a maximum period of 13 years. In some cases also, data is picked after a day's visit to the mental health facility for monthly treatment. Findings are then obtained for analysis, verification, justification and acceptance. Figure 1 gives a diagrammatic view of the method employed for the research.

4.0 Research Findings

4.1 Psychoactives

Once daily activities and actions are mentally and psychologically motivated. Without the mind in its perfect state or one in its absolute complete state of mind, one cannot operate or work very well. So whatever be the case, the head with the brain at its utmost functionality is needed for once daily movements, operations and activities. Anything contrarily to this will result in negative consequences. And in other to achieve mentally ill state or mind of 80% disability state, there

is need for Psychoactives. These are drugs that inhibit the action of the brain or mind resulting in moody, bad behaviour and actions. Some of the Psychoactives includes ethanol, caffeine, cocaine, heroin, wee (weed), cigar, opium etc. When such drugs are taken into the body and subsequently into the mind continuously, coordination of the body by nerves and neurons becomes reduced drastically by percentage. When this happens, the person sense organs such as hearing, feeling, taste, sight etc becomes affected. Continuation of life in a proper manner to help oneself and country is problematic. Use of healthy individuals to heal people of mentally ill status. Psychoactives destruction effects.

4.1.1 Psychoactives destruction Effects

In every community in Ghana, the lower class forms the masses. With a percentage of the mass classified into psychoactive affected people. With such people, the rate at which they drink alcohol (95% in alcohol percentage) for instance is from morning to morning on daily basis. Such people do not have a good eating habit and usually seen as people of no usefulness in the country. Most are met on daily basis undergoing random motion. They do not have the mind set to think through activities. On sense of judgment and direction as well as defined goals and objectives to achieve in life. No daily income or monthly salary to support life and home. Such people are always seen to be living in hideouts because of devious motives and activities. Most of them are very bad people because of the highness in mind due to large intake of

psychoactive. Those with families who think about them end up in mental homes and facilities for rehabilitations.

Sending someone with good mental health state to such a facility and meeting such from a psychoactive background can lead to negative effects. Assuming someone of PHD status whose head has been short through Occultic means and installed in others meet such as person. If such a doctor sense of direction is deactivated and gives up in life, then his is a pilot who will lose total control of his captainship. Such a person will begin to drink excessively, take in all kinds of narcotic drugs, be sexually active to satisfy him/herself and that soul is gone. An entire family, community, nation, world will be flooded unto poverty and self-destruction.

4.2 Occultism Incorporated

Worldwide occultism plays a major role in mentally sick individual's generation into mental health facilities. Some believe in get rich quick schemes hence the use of supernatural means to attain that height. In such get rich world schemes, one does sacrifices hence the possibility of sacrificing a human being for the enrichment in life. What one does is seize a brother, sister, family member or relative or any individuals who has worked for wealth and utilize it aimlessly. The use of all kinds of supernatural means to seize that individual's opportunity in life or breakthrough. They then lay their cross of suffering on the individual or brother to go through their suffering and hustles in life while they enjoy life to the fullest.

The most interesting part is that, they always have such a person in focus and will be monitoring is daily activities.

4.2.1 Occultism incorporated impacts on good health minds

Occultism incorporated effects on healthy mind is total disaster. Most great minds and individuals have lost their lives because of the bad effects of occultism and get rich easy life by people. Some end up as mad people walking in the streets while the Oculitic man or initiator is a beneficiary and enjoying life to a greater extent.

4.3 Street Arrest of Individuals

Street life also forms part of a society activities. Most school drop outs, sellers who have migrated from their local community to cities ends up living on the streets. Life in the streets is like living in the jungle where only the fitters survive. Therefore, people or individuals on the streets are always involved in a fight or all kinds of illegal activities which mostly warrant arrest by police to police stations. Those that ends up in police stations ends up in police cells and those who ends in hospitals ends up in mental health facilities for treatments. They go through all kinds of mental treatments and ends up as mentally ill or retarded patients. This is achieved after series of bad treatment by doctors and nurses who are on their sides or same Oculitic world or the continuous use of mentally ill drugs. Such people ends up losing their minds to a higher degree and final output is madness.

4.3.1 Percentage change and effects from individuals on the streets

In Ghana, street life personnel's or individuals on the streets do not play major roles in national development. Such people are always seen in Ghetto's having their daily activities. They are mostly smokers, gangsters, tricksters, gamblers and involved in all kinds of social vices. In terms of percentage personnel's from the streets to mental health facilities are first of all to a degree of 60% in mental disability. Once they are subjected to mental facilities for rehabilitations, some get rehabilitated into different good kinds of individuals to live a normal life. Those who are unable to return to normalcy goes mad totally or even death. Some are in treasure hunting looking for answers for the good will of treasures for their lives. Spiritual arrest also exists which involves the arrest spiritually for entering and assessing a real one ought not to. This at times also results in mental illness or madness.

4.4 Other kinds of failures

Nature has within its creation failures of various forms. Everyone is bound to fail in one way of the other by a certain percentage. What one does in times of difficulty is the most important thing. Failures can be seen in terms of failed marriages, failed examinations, failure in business, failure in learning a trade, failure at once job, failure in governance etc. all these are different forms of failures. There is a mental havoc associated with all these failures. This may end once remaining life on earth in a mental home or mental facility. When it

happens like this, it's once responsibility to justify before nature and mankind why the failure should not occur, continue and be replaced with success. One ought to fight nature and mankind with whatever means in life to justify his/her cause before natural panelist and mankind. Once justification is well done whichever way and well understood by all, then one can proceed unto success. If not, he/she may end up as a mentally ill person or even goes mad. Defense and justification of a cause is both physically and spiritually. It is likely such an individual has entered into a realm and assessed a great treasure which will lead him unto greater heights in life. Hence the need for spiritual defense because all treasures are spiritually bound. So once such a person is unable to defend or justify why such a treasure belongs to him/her and does have the spiritual power and authority to possess and protect it, he or she may end up mad or mentally retarded.

4.4.1 Effects from other kinds of failures resulting in mental disability

The impacts of mental disability states resulting in all kinds of failures on good mental health states is enormous. As elaborated above, all kinds of failures exist which may end one in a mental home followed by all kinds of consequences. Two main consequence experienced by individuals who finds themselves in such situation is either madness or death. When the failure is continuous and no way to leave the deep pit, some even hung themselves or commits suicides. Those who do not end their lives but continues in the hustles and torchers ends up in mental facilities for rehabilitations and treatments and

later towards madness or death. It is only a few, about 10%, who are able to be rehabilitated in rehabilitation centres by family members and friends. Such friends and families should be willing to spend money towards rehabs. During the rehabilitation process, patients are taken through all kinds of treatments. Some of the vocational training includes kente weaving, instruments playing, clay artistic works etc.

5 Conclusions

Mental disability states generated by any of the scenarios under research findings is a state which can be worked on to attain positive or negative results. Positive results yielding 75% - 80% good mental health state of being is a position of living a new life to help oneself and mankind. Or mentally retarded person with the final results of madness or death. People will continue to smoke, drink alcohol, and take stimulants and psychoactive. This may have effects on the human mind and its final efficiencies in thinking and usage. Meeting physiological needs is very problematic to the average Ghanaian and the world at large. Continuous difficulty in such directions will end people in mental homes and facilities. Assessing treasures in life either through holy or unholy grounds will have people entering into spiritual reals and the resultant ending in mental homes if the nature is unanswered. It is therefore the responsibility of psychiatric doctors, nurses and health professionals to help such people to regain their mental power and strength. There need to be efficacy in treatment and truthfulness on the part of practitioners, drugs administering in taking care of the mentally retarded. Because by the time one

is through with his/her treatment, a drug might have ended someone in mental jail. This is because all the generated scenarios under research findings are feasible and likely to end someone in this mentally disabled state forever. It is therefore the responsibilities of practitioners, traditionalists, faith based and alternative healers, health professionals, mental health workers, media, families and friends and all other stakeholders to help bring back the person to about 84% mentally stable state to help oneself and nation.

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